

A Study of the Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl with some Metal Ions : Part X. N-*p*-Acetamino and N-*p*-Aminobenzenesulphonyl Glycines

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Using N-*p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (R^aH_2) and N-*p*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (R^mH_2) as ligands, complex compounds isolated in the pure states are $Cu(R^aH)(OH)(H_2O)$; $Hg(R^aH)(OH)(H_2O)2H_2O$; $Ag(R^aH)$; $Pb(R^aH)_22H_2O$; $M^{II}(R^mH)_2$ where $M^{II} = Cu(II)$, $Zn(II)$ and $Cd(II)$; $BaCu(R^m)_2$ and $Ag(R^mH)$. Magnetic susceptibility data of all $Cu(II)$ complexes and electronic spectra of $Cu(R^mH)_2$ in alkaline solution as well as of the ligands R^aH_2 and R^mH_2 have been determined and a discussion has been made.

Interesting results obtained with the chelating agent N-*o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine¹, led the present authors to study the reactions and properties of N-*p*-acetaminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (R^aH_2) and N-*p*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine (R^mH_2).

The $Cu(II)$ complexes isolated are $Cu(R^aH)(OH)(H_2O)$ and $Cu(R^mH)_2$. The solution of the complex $Cu(R^mH)_2$ in dil. $NaOH$ decomposes slowly, so the sodium salt could not be obtained. However $BaCu(R^m)_2$ has been prepared by treating the solution of $Cu(R^mH)_2$ in two equivalents of $NaOH$ with a solution of $Ba(NO_3)_2$. With $Ag(I)$ both R^aH_2 and R^mH_2 gave same type of complexes, e.g., $Ag(R^aH)$ and $Ag(R^mH)$ respectively. $Pb(II)$ complex isolated is a bis-chelate, $Pb(R^aH)_22H_2O$. With $Zn(II)$ and $Cd(II)$ complex compounds isolated are $Zn(R^mH)_22H_2O$ and $Cd(R^mH)_2$ respectively.

Magnetic susceptibilities of all $Cu(II)$ complexes have been studied at room temperature. Electronic spectra of R^aH_2 , $R^mH_3^+$ in aqueous solution and with one and two equivalents of $NaOH$ respectively and of $Cu(R^mH)_2$ in alkaline solution have been measured.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. *Preparation of the ligands R^aH_2 and R^mH_2* : N-*p*-Acetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride was condensed with glycine in the usual manner. The ligand R^aH_2 was isolated as white shining crystals. It is soluble in hot water, ethanol and acetone, m.p. 226° . Found: Eq. wt. 273.06; N, 9.93; calc.: Eq. wt., 272; N, 10.30%. The ligand R^mH_2 as R^mH_2 , HCl was prepared by hydrolysing R^aH_2 with dil. HCl following usual procedure², and the resulting

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2. A. I. Vogel, "Text book of practical organic chemistry", p. 1006, Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1956.

solution was filtered, evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH to absorb excess HCl, yellowish-white crystals separated, which were triturated with ethanol, filtered, washed with ethanol to make it free from acetic acid and air dried. It is soluble in water, insoluble in ethanol and acetone, m.p. 209°. Found : Eq. wt., 133.20; N, 10.20; Cl, 13.00; calc.: Eq. wt., 133.27; N, 10.50; Cl, 13.30%.

B. *Complex compounds of Cu(II)* : $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^a\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ isolated as bright green crystals following usual procedure³. The complex $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ was prepared by adding an aqueous solution of R^mH_2 , HCl (2 moles) to an aqueous solution of Cu(II) sulphate (1 mole) and adjusting the pH ≈ 3.0 with NaOH solution, black shining crystals of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ soon separated. The water insoluble compound $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ was dissolved in two equivalents of NaOH solution and a solution of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was added to it, a deep green crystalline solid $\text{Ba Cu}(\text{R}^m)_2$ soon separated, washed with water and ethanol and air dried. Analytical data are reported in Table I.

C. *Complex compounds of Ag(I), Hg(II) and Pb(II)* : They were prepared following the same procedure³. Analytical data are reported in Table I.

D. *Complex compounds of Zn(II) and Cd(II)* : An aqueous solution of R^mH_2 , HCl was added to an aqueous solution containing Zn(II) or Cd(II) and the pH was adjusted to 3.5 ~ 4.0 by adding NaOH solution, shining white crystals separated, washed with water, ethanol and air dried. Analytical data are reported in Table I.

TABLE I
Complex compounds and their analyses

Compound	% Metal		% Nitrogen		Moles of H_2O lost at 105–110°	% Loss at 105–110°	
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.		Found	Reqd.
$\text{Cu}(\text{R}^a\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	17.16	17.19	7.56	7.57	one	5.00	4.87
$\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$	12.06	12.19	10.64	10.74
$\text{BaCu}(\text{R}^m)_2$	9.60	9.68	8.40	8.53	(Ba :	20.50	20.86)
$\text{Ag}(\text{R}^a\text{H})$	28.82	28.49	7.10	7.38
$\text{Ag}(\text{R}^m\text{H})$	32.20	32.05	8.04	8.31
$\text{Hg}(\text{R}^a\text{H})(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	36.80	36.90	5.14	5.16	two	6.90	6.64
$\text{Pb}(\text{R}^a\text{H})_22\text{H}_2\text{O}$	26.35	26.37	7.18	7.13	half	1.14	1.15
$\text{Cd}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$	19.42	19.64	9.60	9.82
$\text{Zn}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_22\text{H}_2\text{O}$	11.66	11.69	10.09	10.12	two	6.11	6.42

Magnetic susceptibility measurements of all Cu(II) complexes were made and data after diamagnetic correction using Pascal's constants are reported in Table II, in which data on electronic spectra of the ligands R^aH_2 and R^mH_2 , HCl and of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ in two equivalents of NaOH are also included.

TABLE II

Magnetic moments of Cu(II) complexes and electronic spectra of some of the compounds

Compound	μ_{eff} in B.M.	Temp. °K	λ_{max}^{aq} in m μ	log ϵ
Cu(R ^a H) (OH) (H ₂ O)	1.82	303
Cu(R ^m H) ₂	1.85	305
Cu(R ^m H) ₂ + two equivalents of NaOH	670	1.71
	261	4.53
	209	4.46
BaCu(R ^m) ₂	1.85	294
R ^a H ₂	259	4.30
	210	4.03
NaR ^a H	259	4.27
	210	4.03
R ^m H ₂ , HCl	298	2.87
	255	1.65
	227	2.82
R ^m H ₂ , HCl + two equivalents of NaOH	262	4.17
	211	3.97

DISCUSSION

The ligand N-benzenesulphonyl glycine and its nitro-derivatives⁴ form both mono as well as bis-chelates with group IB and group IIB metals, while the ligand N-*o*-aminobenzenesulphonyl glycine¹ forms only mono-chelates with Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II). This may be due to the presence of *o*-amino donor group in the ligand which may therefore act as a tridentate one as shown below :—

But with ligand R^mH₂ only *bis*-chelates are formed and the compounds were isolated at comparatively high *pH* values, i.e., (*pH* 3 ~ 4.5) at which the donor property of the *N* atom of the -SO₂NH- group is profoundly increased due to the tendency of the sulphonamido-hydrogen to ionise on coordination⁵.

The magnetic moments of all Cu(II) complexes stated in the paper have normal values. Compounds of the type Cu(RH)₂ have generally subnormal magnetic moment values but normal values are observed on salt formation³. The subnormal magnetic moments of a series of Cu(II) complexes of the type Cu(RH)₂ may be attributed to Cu-Cu interactions

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5. N. N. Ghosh and M. N. Majumder, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 559.

and they are closely comparable to Cu(II) acetate monohydrate⁶. Most of them are sparingly soluble in water and in solution they behave as weak dibasic acids^{3,7} indicated by potentiometric titration. But the compound $\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m\text{H})_2$ is insoluble in water and appears to be an exception in the series, because of its normal magnetic moment value. The *p*-amino group in the ligand molecule is probably responsible in some way for this anomaly.

Absorption band of $\text{Na}_2\text{Cu}(\text{R}^m)_2$ has been found at 670 $m\mu$. This lies within the range 600–900 $m\mu$, generally found for Cu(II) complexes⁸. However ϵ max value supports distorted octahedral arrangement in aqueous solution⁹. Absorption peaks in the u.v. region having high extinction values are undoubtedly due to ligand molecules. In the case of R^aH_2 there is no shift of the bands on treating with alkali, but in the case of R^mH_2 appreciable shifts of the bands towards shorter wavelength are observed, evidently due to the presence of the same species R^aH^- in the former case and in the latter case two different species R^mH_3^+ and R^mH^- respectively.

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